

Evidence-based approaches in toxicology: their origins, challenges, and future directions

Thomas Hartung, Center for Alternatives to Animal Testing (CAAT), Doerenkamp-Zbinden Chair for Evidence-based Toxicology, Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, MD, USA, and University of Konstanz, CAAT-Europe, Germany

Katya Tsaïoun, Evidence-based Toxicology Collaboration, Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, Baltimore, MD

Abstract

Over the last 40 years, Evidence-based practices and methods have revolutionized the practice of medicine, improved the standards of basic clinical research, and led to broad adoption of evidence-based methods in clinical practice due to their transparency, consistency, and reproducibility. About 20 years ago, the first attempts to adapt this methodology to toxicology led to the humble beginnings of Evidence-based Toxicology (EBT). A milestone in this movement was a community-forming conference in Como, Italy, in 2007, which led to formation of the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC) in 2011. EBTC has been building a community of EBT pioneers who are developing and disseminating these concepts. The expanding toolbox of systematic reviews, scoping reviews and evidence maps, is increasingly applied in already several thousand systematic reviews in environmental health. Increasingly, agencies such as the US Environmental Protection Agency, the US Food and Drug Administration and the European Food Safety Authority are actively testing and deploying these tools in their assessments. There are many challenges in adapting evidence-based methodologies from clinical research to toxicology, among them quality assessment of epidemiological, animal and *in vitro* toxicological studies, evidence synthesis and integration across different study types (evidence streams), incorporation of expert judgment, certainty assessment and frameworks for bringing the evidence to regulatory decisions. This paper is looking back at the history of EBT, highlighting the successes and challenges along the way and attempting to map out its future in toxicology and risk assessment.

Keywords

Evidence-based Medicine
Evidence integration
Evidence maps
Objectivity
Regulatory toxicology
Risk assessment
Risk-of-bias analysis
Systematic reviews
Transparency

Key points / Objectives

- Evidence-based medicine has introduced a toolbox for transparency, objectivity and consistency, which is being adapted to toxicology
- Systematic reviews represent the principal tool of EB methods, which is increasingly used in environmental health and regulatory science
- A practice community is growing under the leadership of the Evidence-based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC), which harmonizes the EBT approaches
- Among the many challenges of EBT are the number of diverse evidence types in the literature, lack of reporting standards, lack of evidence integration tools and transparent frameworks that would allow the use of evidence in risk assessment and regulatory decision-making
- The future of EBT is integration of the new computational tools with artificial intelligence (AI) and large language models (LLM), which are poised not only to accelerate systematic reviews but may also be assisting in decision making

Introduction

Today, at least two million articles on biomedical topics are published per year, a number simply overwhelming for clinicians treating patients or decisionmakers developing guidelines for medical treatments. MedLine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/>) alone covers over 5,000 journals with more than 1,000 citations entered daily, in total more than 29 million references. Although on a smaller scale, toxicologists are also facing an ever-growing amount of published information. For example, a simple search in PubMed for term ‘toxicology’ restricted to the year 2023 resulted in 27,603 hits. Consequently, unstructured evidence retrieval by individuals is prone to be subjective and incomplete, often resulting in erroneous, conflicting, biased¹ and non-transparent conclusions². In medicine, the solution to this problem was the implementation of evidence-based (EB) methodologies rooted in transparency, comprehensiveness and objectivity. Hence, Evidence-based Medicine (EBM) was born from the need to extract and synthesize the available evidence from the large amount of information with varied quality on treatments for different health conditions in order to assist physicians to find best treatments for their patients. EBM and its principal tool, systematic review (SR), offered a structured way in which various studies answering the same question could be objectively and transparently selected, assembled, and summarized for physicians and other decision-makers in medicine such as governments and private payer insurance companies.

Implementation of EB methods not only improved decision-making in healthcare, but over time exposed the deficiencies of primary clinical research and led to improvements in design of clinical trials, making randomized controlled clinical trials (RCT) the standard for testing efficacy of medical treatments. This article briefly reviews the origins of evidence-based methodologies, the impact of their implementation in the field of medicine as well as the history, recent progress and barriers to implementation of these methods in the fields of toxicology and environmental health.

The Origins and Fundamentals of Evidence-based Medicine

Any new ideas need a driving force to make measurable progress, and the field of Evidence-based Medicine (EBM) has been driven by Cochrane Collaboration, which grew from ideas Sir Archibald Cochrane presented in a 93-page book titled *Effectiveness and Efficiency: Random Reflections on Health Services* (1972). It took another 20 years before the Cochrane Collaboration was formed in 1993. Around this time, the term “evidence-based” was first used.

Systematic literature reviews (SR) are the principal tool of evidence-based medicine. It is an evidence synthesis methodology that differs considerably from the narrative review that is abundant in science, including medicine and toxicology. Narrative reviews are expert opinions that are important in all scientific disciplines. By taking a 30,000 feet view and drafting the future of the field, they provide a vision for the future of the specific fields, based on the often decades of experience of the authors. However, narrative reviews, even when written by key opinion leaders in the field, lack the comprehensiveness, transparency, rigor, and reproducibility of systematic reviews, which are the key characteristics of EB methodologies. To minimize subjectivity in the selection of evidence, systematic reviews require the up-front definition of the research question, the sources (databases) to be searched, the search terms to be used and inclusion / exclusion criteria. All this, including the study appraisal methodologies and data analysis methods, are defined *a priori* in a published protocol, which is made public before the data analysis is complete, preferably, in a peer-reviewed journal. The results can be qualitative (narrative synthesis) or quantitative³ (meta-)analysis. Meta-analysis statistically integrates individual results from several studies into one overall conclusion⁴. It is important to state that the studies must meet the similarity criteria in terms of design, populations and endpoints, and that meta-analyses are only valid when they are a part of the systematic review.

Study quality assessment plays a crucial role in evidence-based approaches, particularly in the realm of healthcare, policymaking, and research. Quality assessment is used to evaluate the methodological rigor and validity of individual studies. This includes assessing factors such as study design, sample size, control of confounding variables, statistical analyses, and the appropriateness of conclusions drawn from the data. Studies with higher quality are typically increasing the certainty of results in systematic reviews.

The study appraisal component of systematic reviews relies on harmonized frameworks to assess the risk-of-bias of the included studies. An explicit and widely accepted assessment framework is essential to consistently assess the evidence according to its quality and its potential to be skewed by a systematic error, or bias. EBM typically distinguishes five levels of evidence quality ranging from ‘expert opinion’ and case studies, cohort and case-control studies to the highest quality studies, such as randomized clinical trials (RCT). Systematic reviews of RCTs are considered to provide the highest level of evidence. A variety of appraisal tools exist for all clinical fields and evidence levels⁵. Such tools typically provide a list of questions addressing bias domains, which are answered by two reviewers, with a conflict resolution policy in place. Examples of such tools are the Cochrane risk-of-bias tool for RCTs⁶, and ROBINS-I, a tool for assessing risk of bias in non-randomized studies of interventions⁷. The resulting systematic review has to be reported in a structured way, according to PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) statement⁴. There is a separate checklist for reporting diagnostic test accuracy: STARD (STAndards for the Reporting of Diagnostic accuracy studies⁸).

Implementation of evidence-based (EB) methodologies in medicine led to improvement in quality of basic research and transparency and consistency of medical decision. This started by initial unbiased assessment of the state of the field that provided guidance for primary researchers to improve on the study design and minimize the risk of bias. Over time it elevated the scientific rigor, reproducibility and validity of primary research and improved the quality of available evidence on a clinical topic. As a result, EBM⁹ became the standard of clinical practice and the foundation of treatment guidelines development. EBM has now grown to a widely accepted Evidence-based HealthCare (EBHC) approach of reviewing and summarizing clinical interventions in diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment of various clinical conditions on the basis of research evidence, cost of treatment, a physician's clinical expertise and the individual patient's circumstances and values, in order to identify the best practice for each patient. In essence, this approach aims to provide the best and latest available research evidence for the specific patient.

Systematic reviews are designed to minimize bias and provide a comprehensive analysis of the totality of the available evidence, which can lead to surprising findings that may change the way we think about a particular topic. One recent example of such change in medical practice is a systematic review of oral anti-coagulants¹⁰, which concluded that vitamin K antagonists, which were the mainstay of blood coagulation control and stroke prevention in atrial fibrillation patients, were inferior to new anticoagulants, which were more effective, had fewer bleeding episodes and other side effects. This changed the medical practice guidelines, leading to improvements in the outcomes and quality of care for the patients.

In summary, EB methods help elevate the standards of basic research and over time ensure that decisions are based on the best, most reliable, and reproducible evidence.

Why Evidence-based Toxicology and Why Now?

Reliability and reproducibility of evidence as well as quality of research studies are particularly relevant to toxicology right now, since the toxicology is undergoing a revolution spearheaded by advancements in science, which have recently been recognized by US Food and Drug Administration (US FDA) in its 2022 FDA Modernization Act¹¹. Objective structured methodology is urgently needed to compare the ability of the legacy regulatory toxicological tests methods dating from 1950ies and reliant on animal studies in rodents and non-rodent mammals (rabbits, beagle dogs, non-human primates, pigs) with the growing number of tests that are utilizing the new human-biology-based methodologies (human stem cell-derived models, organs on chip (a.k.a., microphysiological systems), genomics, proteomics and other ~omics read-outs, high-throughput and high-content technologies.

The fact that learnings from clinical research are applicable to toxicology has been recognized almost 20 years ago. Indeed, the term "evidence-based toxicology" was first introduced in 2005 by one of the authors in a keynote to the 5th World Conference on Alternative Methods to Animal Experiments in the Life Sciences (Figure 1) in an attempt at translating concepts of evidence-based medicine (EBM) to toxicology. This was based on Sebastian Hoffmann's thesis "Evidence-based *in vitro* Toxicology" (University of Konstanz, 2001-2005, <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:bsz:352-opus-15911>) under supervision of Dr. Thomas Hartung.

Guzelian et al.¹² used the term in the context of determining the causation in toxicology. Simultaneously, Hoffmann and Hartung^{13,14} focused on similarities of toxicological tests assessment and evaluation of diagnostic procedures with the purpose of building confidence in toxicological test methods.

The need for such transparent and more objective approaches in synthesis of toxicological evidence becomes apparent from the early work of Rudén (2001)¹⁵ on trichloroethylene and Golden et al. (2003)¹⁶ on polychlorinated biphenyls. Both studies are reports on risk assessment of chemicals, and demonstrate that incomplete evidence, biases in evidence collection and selection, as well as nontransparent application of “weight of evidence” approaches may easily result in inconsistent and even contradictory decisions.

Despite the recognized need for objective assessment tools in toxicology, the few proposed methods for data appraisal either fall short of providing an objective tool (e.g., Klimisch et al., 1997¹⁷ does not require a justification of the assessment, along with other limitations such as limited guidance) or they have not yet reached a broader audience. Schneider et al. (2009)¹⁸ built on the Klimisch tool, expanded guidance and specifically developed their tools in the context of EBT. They developed and tested appraisal tools for *in vitro* and *in vivo* methods by appraising experiments assessing a range of toxicological papers. Their approach has been tested in (eco-)toxicological studies which are required under the European chemical regulation REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and restriction of Chemicals).

Building on these concepts, it was proposed that toxicology as a science would also benefit from implementation of the core principles of EBM: transparency, objectivity, comprehensiveness, rigor, reproducibility and consistency. It was recognized early on that EBM relies on key tools, which had been little used in toxicology: systematic literature reviews, pre-publishing of study protocols, standardized tools for assessment of quality and risk-of-bias of included studies, and operationalized group decision-making processes, such as evidence-to-decision (EtD) frameworks¹⁹. Instead, toxicology decisions about human and environmental health were still relying entirely on expert judgement and narrative reviews, leading to inconsistencies and poor reproducibility of toxicological studies²⁰. At the same time, the pioneer of EB in toxicology Drs. Kristina Thayer and Andrew Rooney and colleagues at the National Institutes of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS) recognized that systematic reviews have a potential to address reproducibility and quality of toxicological studies and that their implementation is strategically aligned with the NIH-wide reproducibility initiative²¹.

Challenges in translating EBM to toxicology research

While it was recognized that EB methods could be applied to toxicology, the community also acknowledged that there are substantial differences between the nature of clinical and toxicological research. The problems faced in toxicology have different facets than those in medicine. The heterogeneous nature of the toxicological data represents a continuously evolving and complex evidence base that cannot be handled simply by adopting EBM methodology. EBM tools need to be adapted to toxicology and combined with sophisticated methodologies of evidence synthesis, which is an area of intense methodological research.

Variety of study designs is another key aspect of toxicology, which complicates adoption of EB methods and requires careful collaborative development of new tools. In clinical research randomized controlled trials (RCTs) represent the standard type of experimental evidence. RCTs are defined as quantitative, comparative, prospective controlled experiments, in which a group of investigators studies two or more interventions by administering them to groups of individuals, who have been randomly assigned to receive each intervention. In toxicology such studies cannot be conducted on human subjects for ethical reasons, so the type of toxicological evidence is usually limited to animal studies and epidemiological observational human studies. Both of these study types have limitations: in animal studies one can (and should) randomize animals to treatment and a control groups, but the evidence is indirect since one has to extrapolate from animal results to human, and there are substantial documented differences in biology between the species²². The epidemiological studies, on the other hand, do study the effects of a substance in the relevant species, but typically are retrospective and not randomized, which increases the potential for bias in the results.

Gathering toxicology community around EBT concept

To explore these opportunities of application of EB methods to toxicology as well as identify the barriers to their adoption, the First International Forum on Evidence-based Toxicology was convened by Dr. Thomas Hartung and his colleagues at the European Commission of Validation of Alternative Methods (ECVAM) in 2007 in Como, Italy²³ and included over 200 representatives of major international regulatory agencies, academic and industry toxicologists from all continents. It was organized to recognize and address the deficiencies in toxicology and explore ways to address them using EB methodologies. The meeting's participants recognized that toxicology as a science suffers from the lack of transparency or standardization in reporting of methods and results, reliance on expert opinions and narrative reviews to summarize the evidence, and the difficulties in making health-based decisions based on such fragmented, subjectively selected evidence. They explored the potential of evidence-based toxicology and agreed that there is an opportunity to improve the quality of toxicological evidence if EB methods were to be adopted by all stakeholders, while recognizing some barriers to adoption such as the need for adaptation of some EBM tools to toxicological evidence, psychological resistance to new way of conducting research, and the need for a driving force to make change, among others. The meeting participants have agreed on the defining principles of EBT (Table 1) and endorsed The Declaration of Como: *"We, the undersigned participants of the First International Forum Towards EBT, commit to the further development, refinement and application of Evidence Based Toxicology (EBT) as described in the Defining Characteristics agreed during the Forum. We invite the scientific community and other stakeholders to join with us in this effort."*

The next key event in EBT was the 2010 conference '21st Century Validation for 21st Century Tools'²⁴ at Johns Hopkins University in 2011, which led to the creation of the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC, <http://www.ebtox.org>), which was conceived by some of the participants of the meeting in Como headed by Dr. Thomas Hartung, who became the Chair for Evidence-based Toxicology at Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health. EBTC was conceived as an open membership organization that brings together all the toxicology stakeholders committed to fostering, development, and application of EB methods to

toxicology. Over the next decade EBTC has become the driving force for EBT movement, akin to Cochrane Collaboration in Evidence-based Medicine movement, and now is a network organization with hundreds of active members which include research, regulatory and industry leaders, united in their vision to improve public health, as well as understand and reduce human impact on the environment by bringing evidence-based approaches to chemical safety sciences. By facilitating the modernization of the toxicological toolbox, reinvigorating the safety sciences, and integrating evidence-based approaches into decision-making, EBTC's ultimate ambition is that all stakeholders in government, industry, academia, and the general public will be able to have more confidence and trust in the processes by which scientific evidence is assembled, selected and evaluated when addressing questions related to the safety of chemicals to human health and the environment.

EBTC is conducting research through its working groups where members of EBTC network can initiate and collaborate on solving EBT methodological challenges, conducting systematic reviews and collaboratively developing and validating tools for the community. The first EBTC stakeholder meeting was held in 2012²⁵. One of the first products of EBTC were developing the primer on conducting systematic reviews in toxicology²⁶ and a guidance on assessing the methodological and reporting quality of toxicological studies⁵.

Over the last decade, a growing number of researchers have started to test application of various EBM approaches to toxicology (see Fig. 2 for timeline of key events in EBT). The early attempts also had some stumbling blocks in application of SR and other EBM tools to toxicological studies and pointed to the need for new tools to be developed and validated by the community has been identified²⁷. Major milestones in developing the tools were the adoption of this approach by major regulatory agencies. EFSA's guidance on use of systematic review to food and feed safety assessment²⁸ pioneered the adoption of this powerful methodology. Then the 2014 Navigation Guide²⁹, led by Dr. Tracy Woodruff, had provided the guidance for conducting SRs of epidemiological studies. while National Toxicology Program Office of Health Assessment and Translation (NTP OHAT) under the leadership of Dr. Andrew Rooney published the *Handbook for Conducting a Literature-Based Health Assessment Using OHAT Approach for Systematic Review and Evidence Integration*.³²

In parallel and in collaboration with the agencies' pioneers of systematic reviews, EBTC has led the efforts on application of EBM methods to toxicological methods comparison, building on the Cochrane methods developed in the field of evidence-based evaluation of diagnostic tests³³. EBTC has conducted pioneering systematic reviews in assessing the performance of zebrafish embryotoxicity³⁴ and comparing the performance of animal, human and *in vitro* toxicological methods in prediction of human drug-induced liver injury (DILI)³⁵. The studies provided a framework to objectively assess the new methods and support their implementation in the context of the vision '*Toxicity Testing for the 21st Century – a Vision and a Strategy*'³⁶, where evidence-based toxicology methods are expected to accelerate the evaluation of and implementation of new toxicological test methods³⁷.

This collaborative work by EBTC and its stakeholders has paved the way for thousands of systematic reviews in environmental health and, importantly, major international regulatory agencies such as European Food Safety Authority, US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)

and divisions of US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) now are actively using systematic reviews and EB methods in their assessments.

The Key Applications of EBT

Several priority areas with the immediate application of EBT have been identified:

1. Systematic scoping reviews, evidence maps and knowledge graphs to facilitate evidence-based approaches to decision-making in chemicals policy and wider environmental health^{38,39}.
2. Systematic literature reviews of safety of a given chemical.
3. Integration of heterogeneous toxicological information on a given substance, e.g., as required for risk assessment purposes.
4. Evaluation of toxicological test methods to identify their applicability domains, ability to predict human toxicity and their limitations, analogous to the evaluation of clinical diagnostic tests^{13, 35, 27}.
5. Evidence-to-decision frameworks that allow the regulators to make decisions about public and environmental health objectively, transparently and considering all the aspects that are important for the public, governments and the health of the planet.

Evidence-based Methods for Pathway-based Approaches in Toxicology

One key area of application of EBM methods to toxicology is comparison of toxicological test methods (animal vs. in vitro and their relevance to prediction of human toxicity endpoints). EBM's diagnostic test assessment has developed several approaches to remedy this situation, some of which have already been proposed for use in toxicology. Methodology has been maturing in the field of evidence-based evaluation of diagnostic tests³³ and these advancements have considerable potential for application in toxicology, in particular, toxicological test methods comparison.⁴⁰ The problem with applying this methodology to the toxicological tests comparison is the lack of appropriate reference standard as controlled prospective studies in human subjects are not ethical to perform. At least a partial solution to the reference standard problem can be found in the emerging field of pathway-based toxicology as proposed in the National Academy of Sciences' 2007 report on "*Toxicity Testing for the 21st Century, A Vision and a Strategy*". Pathway-based tests can be referenced to human biology, which would minimize or eliminate extrapolations from an animal model to humans and their inevitable species differences. The development of pathways of toxicology are greatly facilitated by the application of evidence-based approaches as shown by de Vries et al.⁴¹. Pathway-based methods should be developed according to transparent and objective quality standards. Evaluating their performance is complicated, as most pathway-based methods are high-content, generating large quantities of data. This evidence should be reviewed systematically, appraised, and synthesized in the contexts of both performance assessment and later, in routine use. Furthermore, the integration of the evidence into toxicological practice will require computational tools, which should be reproducible, consistent and transparent. Here, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) approaches could be very useful in processing and summarizing vast amounts of diverse data. This contrasts with the current

practice of weight of evidence (WoE) approaches (Weed, 2005) in toxicological decision-making, which often lack objectivity, transparency and are difficult or impossible to reproduce.

The Key Challenges in Application of EB methods in Toxicology

There were many challenges that met the pioneers of application of systematic review and evidence-based methods in toxicology. The main challenge was adaptation of EBM methods developed for RCTs to the heterogeneous study designs (epidemiological, observational, “natural experiments”) and, even more challenging, to different species and types of studies (*in vivo*⁴⁰, *in vitro*⁴², *in silico*) that comprise the toxicological evidence. Integration of this diverse set of studies to derive a toxicity value, for example, is very challenging, but is being addressed by the community⁴³. Many challenges remain, such as outlined below:

1. Quality, reproducibility and reliability of toxicological studies (*in vivo*, *in vitro*, *in silico*)^{34,35}.
2. Risk-of-bias tools for epidemiological *in vivo*⁷, animal *in vivo*, *in vitro*⁴² and *in silico* studies.
3. Determination of certainty of the body of evidence coming from heterogeneous sources⁴⁴.
 - i. Intense work is being done by toxicology stakeholders on adaptation of GRADE methodology (Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development, and Evaluation)¹⁹ to nonclinical toxicological studies.
4. Introducing systematic literature review step to design and validation of Adverse Outcome Pathways⁴¹.
5. Open science, FAIR data and data interoperability in toxicology^{45–48}.

EBTC is facilitating the work in these challenge areas through its working groups in order to address the gaps to be able to fully implement Evidence-Based Toxicology methods and principles across the ecosystem (Table 2).

Progress of Evidence-based Toxicology

With the publication of the EBTC primer for systematic review in toxicology in 2017²⁶, a standard was set to harmonize evidence-based approaches for safety sciences. Wolffe et al. (2019)³⁹ expanded this to systematic evidence maps. Semi-automated tools for systematic reviews based on machine learning are being increasingly used by researchers and practitioners of systematic reviews (e.g., SWIFT-Review^{49,50}, SysRev⁵¹ and Distiller⁵²). Using the test case of the zebrafish assay for reproductive toxicity and comparing it to the respective regulatory rodent test, valuable experiences were gained and challenges identified as to the application of systematic reviews for the evaluation of test methods^{27,34}. Evidence integration from various evidence streams has become a critical area where collaboration is needed^{53,54}. The increasing uptake of EBT approaches by international regulatory agencies EFSA⁵³ US EPA⁵⁵ US FDA⁵⁶ paves the way to wider adoption by other regulatory agencies around the world. One of the key objectives of EBT is harmonizing the methods, disseminating the knowledge about EB methods and educating the community on the subject. To address that, a 13-lecture class on EBT is taught at Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health and is made available on COURSERA (<https://www.coursera.org/learn/evidence-based-toxicology>). As of writing this article, more than 8,500 learners have enrolled in the first five years.

Conclusions

Evidence-based methods are increasingly adapted and adopted to toxicology and environmental health from the fields of medicine and healthcare. A transition of the toxicology as a field to an evidence-based science is needed to increase relevance, reproducibility, and transparency of the risk assessment. In the light of the toxicology for the 21st century and transition of the field to New Approach Methods (NAMs), poised to revolutionize regulatory science. Hence, toxicology's current heavy reliance on (1) animal models, which have never been systematically evaluated, (2) subjective (narrative) evidence review practices, and (3) expert-based weight-of-evidence (WoE) evaluations need to be critically reassessed with evidence-based methods. Such critical assessment and transition will advance toxicology as a scientific field and thereby facilitate the inclusion of the ever-increasing amount of information and the new technologies in the evidence base. EBT is poised to serve a quality assurance tool when implementing the vision of toxicology for the 21st century⁵⁷.

Fundamental work has been carried out thus far to explore and apply the EBT tools. Thousands of systematic reviews addressing individual chemicals and the associated human, animal, and *in vitro* data are available, but systematic, transparent, and objective reviews of test methods as undertaken in clinical research and diagnostics are still waiting to be adopted by the community at large and, importantly, by OECD and many regulatory agencies. Increasingly, approaches to systematically assess the quality of (eco)toxicological evidence are being tested in ecology⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰.

The crucial step in EB methodology is the evidence synthesis and, as such, it presents a particular challenge in EBT due to the heterogeneity of the evidence streams. Evidence synthesis methodologies in toxicology are central to some of the most intense work in EBT due to its complexity and importance in driving regulatory judgments. Fueled by European policy, novel approaches to integrating evidence from a variety of information sources are being developed. Building on the mechanistic knowledge, the fundamental properties of these emerging frameworks are largely consistent with evidence-based methodologies^{31,57}.

EBT provides essential methodological tools and approaches for 21st century toxicology^{27,35,41}, especially in light of the widely accepted pathway-based vision for a new toxicology. Systematic evidence maps methodology is becoming the foundation of the evidence-based evaluation of biological pathways leading to toxicity. Evidence-based methodologies will allow to objectively compare the human-biology-based tests to legacy animal-based toxicological tests. Finally, evidence synthesis methodologies and evidence-to-decision frameworks tailored to toxicology and environmental health will provide the urgently needed 21st century tools spearheading the implementation of the vision of a new toxicology and revolutionizing safety sciences across clinical, consumer products and occupational applications.

All this work that needs to be conducted requires the driving force to collaboratively develop, harmonize, disseminate the information and assure compliance with various tools. EBTC is leading the work in this space building the community of stakeholders of evidence-based toxicology. Over the past decade EBTC has become a driving force for the community coordinating the work to develop and test EB tools, disseminate the results of systematic, transparent, and objective evidence-based approaches in toxicology^{38,61,62}.

However, the problems faced in toxicology have different facets than those in medicine. The heterogeneous nature of the toxicological data represents a continuously evolving and complex evidence base that cannot be handled simply by adopting EBM methodology. EBM tools need to be adapted to toxicology and combined with sophisticated methodologies of evidence synthesis, which is an area of intense methodological research.

EUROPEAN COMMISSION
DIRECTORATE GENERAL
Joint Research Centre

EFVAM

The gift from validation to life sciences

Validation of alternative tests is one of the rare examples of quality assurance in biomedical research (relevance, not only reproducibility)

“Evidence-based medicine goes in vitro!”

Evidence-based Toxicology
= know how good the test is, which you apply

Tools:

- **Validation studies**
- **Quality assurance (GLP, GCCP)**
- **Systematic review & Meta-analysis**

Joint Research Centre

ihp

Figure 1. The first call to the scientific community to create Evidence-based Toxicology (EBT) in 2005.

In a keynote at the 5th World Congress on Alternatives and Animal Use in the Life Sciences was a memorable event at which 970 colleagues from 46 countries met on August 21-25, 2005, in Berlin (Germany), Thomas Hartung called on the scientific community using this slide to create EBT to assess new and traditional methods.

Figure 2. Timeline of evidence-based toxicology movement. Abbreviations: EBT- Evidence-based Toxicology; EBTC – Evidence-based Toxicology Collaboration; EFSA – European Food Safety Authority; US EPA – US Environmental Protection Agency; US EPA IRIS – US EPA Integrated Risk Information System; GRADE - The Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation working group; US EPA TSCA – 2016 Frank R. Lautenberg Chemical Safety for the 21st Century Act, updating the US EPA Toxic Substances Control Act; SR – systematic review; UCSF – University of California San Francisco.

Table 1

Ten defining characteristics of EBT⁶³

1. Promotes the consistent use of transparent and systematic processes to reach robust conclusions and sound judgments
2. Addresses societal values and expectations and is socially responsible
3. Displays a willingness to check the assumptions upon which current toxicological practice is based to facilitate continuous improvement
4. Recognizes the need to provide for the effective training and development of professional toxicologists
5. Acknowledges a requirement for new and improved tools for critical evaluation and quantitative integration of scientific evidence
6. Embraces all aspects of toxicological practice, and all types of evidence of which use is made in hazard identification, risk assessment, and retrospective analyses of causation
7. Ensures the generation and use of best scientific evidence
8. Includes all branches of toxicological science: human health assessment, environmental and ecotoxicology, and clinical toxicology
9. Acknowledges and builds upon the achievements and contributions of Evidence-Based Medicine/Evidence-Based Health Care

10. Fosters the integration of expert judgment with best possible external evidence

Table 2

EBTC Working Groups	Priority areas	Example collaborative projects
Research Methods	Validity, utility, and transparency of primary research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Framework for evaluation of study validity • Tool for peer-review of in vitro research • New generation risk assessment • Guidance on SR protocols development
Evidence Synthesis	Developing and using SR and evidence mapping methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of SR protocols • Consensus on minimum standards for SRs • Analysis of SR frameworks
Open Science	Ecosystem facilitating finding and reusing each others' data and methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open (FAIR) data infrastructure • Toxicology / EH ontology
Evidence to Decision	Connection between research and policy decisions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First evidence-to-decision framework for occupational and EH

References

1. Wandall, B., Hansson, S. O. & Rudén, C. Bias in toxicology. *Arch. Toxicol.* **81**, 605–617 (2007).
2. Schreider, J. *et al.* Enhancing the credibility of decisions based on scientific conclusions: transparency is imperative. *Toxicol. Sci. Off. J. Soc. Toxicol.* **116**, 5–7 (2010).
3. Egger, M., Smith, G. D. & Phillips, A. N. Meta-analysis: principles and procedures. *BMJ* **315**, 1533–1537 (1997).
4. Page, M. J. *et al.* The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* **372**, n71 (2021).
5. Samuel, G. O. *et al.* Guidance on assessing the methodological and reporting quality of toxicologically relevant studies: A scoping review. *Environ. Int.* **92–93**, 630–646 (2016).
6. Sterne, J. A. C. *et al.* RoB 2: a revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials. *BMJ* **366**, l4898 (2019).

7. Sterne, J. A. *et al.* ROBINS-I: a tool for assessing risk of bias in non-randomised studies of interventions. *BMJ* **355**, i4919 (2016).
8. Cohen, J. F. *et al.* STARD 2015 guidelines for reporting diagnostic accuracy studies: explanation and elaboration. *BMJ Open* **6**, e012799 (2016).
9. Sackett, D. L., Rosenberg, W. M., Gray, J. A., Haynes, R. B. & Richardson, W. S. Evidence based medicine: what it is and what it isn't. *BMJ* **312**, 71–72 (1996).
10. Khouja, C. *et al.* Oral anticoagulants: a systematic overview of reviews on efficacy and safety, genotyping, self-monitoring, and stakeholder experiences. *Syst. Rev.* **11**, 232 (2022).
11. Sen. Paul, R. [R-K. FDA Modernization Act 2.0. <http://www.congress.gov/bill/117th-congress/senate-bill/5002/text> (2022).
12. Guzelian, P. S., Victoroff, M. S., Halmes, N. C., James, R. C. & Guzelian, C. P. Evidence-based toxicology: a comprehensive framework for causation. *Hum. Exp. Toxicol.* **24**, 161–201 (2005).
13. Hoffmann, S. & Hartung, T. Diagnosis: toxic!--trying to apply approaches of clinical diagnostics and prevalence in toxicology considerations. *Toxicol. Sci. Off. J. Soc. Toxicol.* **85**, 422–428 (2005).
14. Hoffmann, S. & Hartung, T. Toward an evidence-based toxicology. *Hum. Exp. Toxicol.* **25**, 497–513 (2006).
15. Rudén, C. The use and evaluation of primary data in 29 trichloroethylene carcinogen risk assessments. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol. RTP* **34**, 3–16 (2001).
16. Golden, R., Doull, J., Waddell, W. & Mandel, J. Potential human cancer risks from exposure to PCBs: a tale of two evaluations. *Crit. Rev. Toxicol.* **33**, 543–580 (2003).

17. Klimisch, H. J., Andreae, M. & Tillmann, U. A systematic approach for evaluating the quality of experimental toxicological and ecotoxicological data. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol. RTP* **25**, 1–5 (1997).
18. Schneider, K. *et al.* 'ToxRTool', a new tool to assess the reliability of toxicological data. *Toxicol. Lett.* **189**, 138–144 (2009).
19. Alonso-Coello, P. *et al.* GRADE Evidence to Decision (EtD) frameworks: a systematic and transparent approach to making well informed healthcare choices. 1: Introduction. *BMJ* **353**, i2016 (2016).
20. Miller, G. W. Improving Reproducibility in Toxicology. *Toxicol. Sci.* **139**, 1–3 (2014).
21. Thayer Kristina A. *et al.* Intersection of Systematic Review Methodology with the NIH Reproducibility Initiative. *Environ. Health Perspect.* **122**, A176–A177 (2014).
22. Chu, X., Bleasby, K. & Evers, R. Species differences in drug transporters and implications for translating preclinical findings to humans. *Expert Opin. Drug Metab. Toxicol.* **9**, 237–252 (2013).
23. Griesinger, C., Hoffmann, S., Kinsner, A., Coecke, S. & Hartung, T. Special issue: Evidence-based toxicology (EBT). Preface. *Hum. Exp. Toxicol.* **28**, 83–86 (2009).
24. Hartung, T. Evidence-based toxicology - the toolbox of validation for the 21st century? *ALTEX* **27**, 253–263 (2010).
25. Stephens, M. L. *et al.* Evidence-based toxicology for the 21st century: opportunities and challenges. *ALTEX* **30**, 74–103 (2013).
26. Hoffmann, S. *et al.* A primer on systematic reviews in toxicology. *Arch. Toxicol.* **91**, 2551–2575 (2017).

27. Stephens, M. L. *et al.* Adaptation of the Systematic Review Framework to the Assessment of Toxicological Test Methods: Challenges and Lessons Learned With the Zebrafish Embryotoxicity Test. *Toxicol. Sci. Off. J. Soc. Toxicol.* **171**, 56–68 (2019).
28. Application of systematic review methodology to food and feed safety assessments to support decision making. *EFSA J.* **8**, 1637 (2010).
29. Lam, J. *et al.* The Navigation Guide - evidence-based medicine meets environmental health: integration of animal and human evidence for PFOA effects on fetal growth. *Environ. Health Perspect.* **122**, 1040–1051 (2014).
30. Handbook for Conducting Systematic Reviews for Health Effects Evaluations.
<https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/whatwestudy/assessments/noncancer/handbook/index.html>.
31. Handbook for Conducting a Literature-Based Health Assessment Using OHAT Approach for Systematic Review and Evidence Integration. (2019).
32. Rooney, A. A., Boyles, A. L., Wolfe, M. S., Bucher, J. R. & Thayer, K. A. Systematic review and evidence integration for literature-based environmental health science assessments. *Environ. Health Perspect.* **122**, 711–718 (2014).
33. Knottnerus, J. A., van Weel, C. & Muris, J. W. M. Evaluation of diagnostic procedures. *BMJ* **324**, 477–480 (2002).
34. Hoffmann, S. *et al.* A Systematic Review to Compare Chemical Hazard Predictions of the Zebrafish Embryotoxicity Test With Mammalian Prenatal Developmental Toxicity. *Toxicol. Sci. Off. J. Soc. Toxicol.* **183**, 14–35 (2021).
35. Dirven, H. *et al.* Performance of preclinical models in predicting drug-induced liver injury in humans: a systematic review. *Sci. Rep.* **11**, 6403 (2021).

36. Krewski, D., Andersen, M. E., Mantus, E. & Zeise, L. Toxicity testing in the 21st century: implications for human health risk assessment. *Risk Anal. Off. Publ. Soc. Risk Anal.* **29**, 474–479 (2009).
37. Hartung, T. A Toxicology for the 21st Century—Mapping the Road Ahead. *Toxicol. Sci.* **109**, 18–23 (2009).
38. Wolffe, T. A. M., Vidler, J., Halsall, C., Hunt, N. & Whaley, P. A Survey of Systematic Evidence Mapping Practice and the Case for Knowledge Graphs in Environmental Health and Toxicology. *Toxicol. Sci.* **175**, 35–49 (2020).
39. Wolffe, T. A. M., Whaley, P., Halsall, C., Rooney, A. A. & Walker, V. R. Systematic evidence maps as a novel tool to support evidence-based decision-making in chemicals policy and risk management. *Environ. Int.* **130**, 104871 (2019).
40. Hooijmans, C. R. *et al.* SYRCLE’s risk of bias tool for animal studies. *BMC Med. Res. Methodol.* **14**, 43 (2014).
41. De Vries, R. B. M. *et al.* Applying evidence-based methods to the development and use of adverse outcome pathways. *ALTEX* **38**, 336–347 (2021).
42. Roth, N., Zilliacus, J. & Beronius, A. Development of the SciRAP Approach for Evaluating the Reliability and Relevance of in vitro Toxicity Data. *Front. Toxicol.* **3**, 746430 (2021).
43. Schaefer, H. R. & Myers, J. L. Guidelines for performing systematic reviews in the development of toxicity factors. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol. RTP* **91**, 124–141 (2017).
44. Brozek, J. L. *et al.* GRADE Guidelines 30: the GRADE approach to assessing the certainty of modeled evidence—An overview in the context of health decision-making. *J. Clin. Epidemiol.* **129**, 138–150 (2021).

45. Watford, S., Edwards, S., Angrish, M., Judson, R. S. & Paul Friedman, K. Progress in data interoperability to support computational toxicology and chemical safety evaluation. *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* **380**, 114707 (2019).
46. Saarimäki, L. A., Melagraki, G., Afantitis, A., Lynch, I. & Greco, D. Prospects and challenges for FAIR toxicogenomics data. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **17**, 17–18 (2022).
47. Briggs, K. *et al.* Guidelines for FAIR sharing of preclinical safety and off-target pharmacology data. *ALTEX* **38**, 187–197 (2021).
48. Cronin, M. T. D. *et al.* Making in silico predictive models for toxicology FAIR. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol. RTP* **140**, 105385 (2023).
49. SWIFT-Review. *Sciome* <https://www.sciome.com/swift-review/>.
50. Howard, B. E. *et al.* SWIFT-Review: a text-mining workbench for systematic review. *Syst. Rev.* **5**, 87 (2016).
51. Bozada, T. *et al.* Sysrev: A FAIR Platform for Data Curation and Systematic Evidence Review. *Front. Artif. Intell.* **4**, 685298 (2021).
52. Gartlehner, G. *et al.* Assessing the accuracy of machine-assisted abstract screening with DistillerAI: a user study. *Syst. Rev.* **8**, 277 (2019).
53. Authority, E. F. S. EFSA Scientific Colloquium 23 – Joint European Food Safety Authority and Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration Colloquium Evidence integration in risk assessment: the science of combining apples and oranges 25–26 October 2017 Lisbon, Portugal. *EFSA Support. Publ.* **15**, 1396E (2018).
54. Farhat, N. *et al.* Systematic review in evidence-based risk assessment. *ALTEX* **39**, 463–479 (2022).

55. US EPA, O. Draft Protocol for Systematic Review in TSCA Risk Evaluations.
<https://www.epa.gov/assessing-and-managing-chemicals-under-tsca/draft-protocol-systematic-review-tsca-risk-evaluations> (2018).
56. Schaefer, H. R. *et al.* A systematic review of adverse health effects associated with oral cadmium exposure. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol. RTP* **134**, 105243 (2022).
57. Hartung, T., Hoffmann, S. & Stephens, M. Mechanistic validation. *ALTEX* **30**, 119–130 (2013).
58. Ames, J., Miragem, A. A., Cordeiro, M. F., Cerezer, F. O. & Loro, V. L. Effects of glyphosate on zebrafish: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Ecotoxicol. Lond. Engl.* **31**, 1189–1204 (2022).
59. Gambardella, C. & Pinsino, A. Nanomaterial Ecotoxicology in the Terrestrial and Aquatic Environment: A Systematic Review. *Toxics* **10**, 393 (2022).
60. Varea, R., Piovano, S. & Ferreira, M. Knowledge gaps in ecotoxicology studies of marine environments in Pacific Island Countries and Territories - A systematic review. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* **156**, 111264 (2020).
61. Hoffmann, S., Whaley, P. & Tsaioun, K. How evidence-based methodologies can help identify and reduce uncertainty in chemical risk assessment. *ALTEX* **39**, 175–182 (2022).
62. Whaley, P. *et al.* Recommendations for the conduct of systematic reviews in toxicology and environmental health research (COSTER). *Environ. Int.* **143**, 105926 (2020).
63. Hartung, T. Food for thought... on evidence-based toxicology. *ALTEX* **26**, 75–82 (2009).